

Studies on 4, 4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl Sulfone and 4, 4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl Ether

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The synthesis of bi(6-flavonyl)sulfone and bi(2- and 3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl)sulfone from 4, 4'-dihydroxy diphenyl sulfone and that of bi(6-chromonyl) ether and its 2-methyl and 2-methyl-3-acetyl derivatives, bi(6-flavonyl) ether and bi(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) ether from 4, 4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether have been described.

IN continuation² of our previous work on 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane¹ we have now synthesised some oxygen heterocycles from 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone³ and 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl ether.

For the synthesis of bi(6-flavonyl)sulfone (Ia) the required intermediate 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone was obtained though the Fries migration of 4,4'-diacetoxydiphenyl sulfone. The structure was established by preparing the same compound by the oxidation of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfide with hydrogen peroxide according to Kulkarni³. This was further confirmed by the oxidation of the dimethyl ether of the diacetyl sulfone with alkaline potassium permanganate to the known 4,4'-dimethoxydiphenyl sulfone-3,3'-dicarboxylic acid⁴.

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone was condensed with benzaldehyde in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The bichalconyl derivative so obtained on cyclisation and dehydrogenation with selenium dioxide gave bi(6-flavonyl) sulfone.

The synthesis of bi(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) sulfone (IIa) has been achieved by condensing 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone with ethyl bromoacetate. The 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-di(carbomethoxy) diphenyl sulfone obtained was hydrolysed to the corresponding dicarboxylic acid. This was then heated with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride when through simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation the desired benzofuran derivative was obtained. For the synthesis of bi(2-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) sulfone (IIb), 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone was converted into its diallyloxy derivative and this was converted into 3,3'-diallyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone by heating with diphenyl ether. The allyl phenol was converted into its acetoxy derivative and then brominated. The tetrabromo derivative was subjected to the action of potassium hydroxide in

alcohol according to Kaufman *et al*⁵ when the desired benzofuran derivative was obtained.

Attempt to prepare 3,3'-diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl sulfone by direct formylation of 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone with hexamine or with dimethyl formamide did not succeed.

Some oxygen heterocycles have also been synthesised from 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl ether. The intermediate 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl ether required was obtained through the Fries migration of 4,4'-diacetoxy diphenyl ether. On condensation with ethyl acetate in the presence of pulverised sodium, it gave directly bi(2-methyl-6-chromonyl) ether (Ib). The Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of the same ketone gave bi(2-methyl-3-acetyl-6-chromonyl) ether (Ic). The synthesis of bi(6-chromonyl) ether was achieved through cyanoethylation of 4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether with acrylonitrile. 4,4'-Dicyanoethoxy diphenyl ether obtained, on hydrolysis gave the corresponding acid, which was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid to bi(6-chromanonyl) ether which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal resulted in bi(6-chromonyl) ether (Id).

The condensation of 4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether with either malic acid in the presence of sulphuric acid or with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of different condensing agents like conc. sulphuric acid, anhydrous aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene at 130° and in boiling diphenyl ether did not succeed.

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether was condensed with diethyl carbonate in the presence of pulverised sodium to get bi(4-hydroxy-6-coumarinyl) ether.

The synthesis of bi(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) (IIc) has been achieved by condensing 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether with ethyl bromoac-

tate, hydrolysis of the diester obtained to the corresponding dicarboxylic acid and heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride when simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation gave the desired benzofuran derivative.

Biflavonyl ethers such as hinokiflavone⁶ are found to occur in nature and it was therefore thought of interest to synthesize bi(6-flavonyl) ether from 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl ether as an illustration of a new approach towards the synthesis of such compounds. This was converted into its dibenzoyloxy derivative by reacting it with benzoyl chloride. This rearranged to 3,3'-di(benzoyl-acetyl)-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether with pyridine and powdered potassium hydroxide. The cyclisation of the diketone with conc. sulphuric acid gave bi(6-flavonyl)ether (Ie).

Attempt to formylate 4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether with hexamine with a view to obtain the 3,3'-diformyl derivative required for the synthesis of other oxygen heterocycles did not succeed.

Experimental

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone : A mixture of 4,4'-diacetoxydiphenyl sulfone (1 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 150-60° for 5 hrs. and the product obtained on addition of ice-cold hydrochloric acid was taken up in sodium hydroxide solution. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from acetic acid in light brown needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 189-190°. It gave a red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride (Found : C, 57.59 ; H, 4.06, C₁₆H₁₄O₆S requires C, 57.50 ; H, 4.19%.)

The di(2,4-DNP) : Prepared as usual and crystallised from diphenyl ether in orange needles gave m.p. 305-06°. (Found : N, 16.00 C₂₆H₂₂N₆O₁₂S requires N, 16.14%.)

The dimethyl ether : A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl sulfone (1 g.), dimethyl sulfate (1.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) in dry acetone was refluxed for 12 hr. The solvent was removed and water added. The product obtained crystallised from alcohol in white shining plates (0.8 g.), m.p. 179°. (Found : C, 59.87 ; H, 4.89, C₁₈H₁₈O₆S requires C, 59.68 ; H, 4.97%.)

Oxidation : 4,4'-Dimethoxydiphenyl sulfone-3,3' dicarboxylic acid was obtained by refluxing the above dimethyl ether (0.5 g.) with potassium permanganate (2 g.) and potassium hydroxide solution (20 ml ; 10%) for 6 hr. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 252° (decomp.) Kolhatkar and Bokil⁴ reported, m.p. 250° (decomp.)

Bi(6'-hydroxy-3'-chalconyl) sulfone : A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone (1 g) benzaldehyde (2.5 g) and potassium hydroxide (5 g in 5 ml water) in alcohol (30 ml) was kept at room

temperature for 24 hr. It was then diluted with water and acidified. The solid obtained crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 208-210°, yield 0.5 g. It gave red colour with conc. sulphuric acid and a positive Wilson test. It also showed a single spot in TLC. (Found : C, 70.53 ; H, 4.34, C₃₀H₂₂O₆S requires C, 70.60 ; H, 4.31%.)

Bi(6'-methoxy-3'-chalconyl) sulfone : Prepared by refluxing a mixture of the above chalcone (0.5 g), dimethyl sulfate (0.8 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) in dry acetone for 15 hr. and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates (0.3 g.) gave m.p. 175-77°. (Found : C, 71.03 ; H, 4.75, C₃₂H₂₆O₆S requires C, 71.36 ; H, 4.83%.)

Bi(6-flavonyl) sulfone : Bi(6'-hydroxy-3' chalconyl) sulfone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (3 g.) in iso-amyl alcohol (50 ml) for 25 hr. It was then filtered hot. The filtrate was cooled and diluted with excess of petroleum ether. The separated product, crystallised from acetic acid gave m.p. 324-226°, yield 0.1 g. It gave a light blue fluorescence with conc. sulfuric acid (Found : C, 71.53 ; H, 3.40, C₃₀H₁₈O₆S requires C, 71.13 ; H, 3.56%.) IR. 1645 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) ; UV λ_{max} 268, 296 nm.

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-di(carbomethoxy) diphenyl sulfone :

A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone (2 g), ethyl bromoacetate (2.5 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g) was refluxed in dry acetone for 15 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in white needles (1g.) m.p. 139-40°. (Found : C, 57.38; H, 5.16. C₂₄H₂₄O₁₀S requires C, 56.91 ; 5.14%.)

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-di(carboxymethoxy) diphenyl sulfone :

The above ester (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid (15 ml) for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in water and the separated product was purified by sodium bicarbonate treatment. The product obtained on acidification of the bicarbonate extract crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles (0.5 g), m.p. 222° (decomp.) (Found : C, 53.40 ; H, 3.80, C₂₀H₁₈O₁₀S requires C, 53.34 ; H, 4.00%.)

Bi(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) sulfone : Obtained from the above dicarboxylic acid (0.5 g) by refluxing with sodium acetate (2 g) and acetic anhydride (8 ml) for 1 hr. and crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale-brown needles (0.1 g) gave m.p. 152-153°. (Found : C, 66.13 ; H, 4.00, C₁₈H₁₄O₄S requires C, 66.26 ; H, 4.29%) IR 885 cm⁻¹ (furan ring breathing) UV λ_{max} (chloroform) 248, 284 nm.

4,4'-Diallyloxydiphenyl sulfone : A mixture of 4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl sulfone (1 g), allyl bromide (1.2 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g)

was refluxed in dry acetone for 8 hr. The solvent was removed and water was added. The product obtained, crystallised from alcohol in white shining plates (0.7 g), m.p. 141-42°. (Found : C, 65.61 ; H, 5.16, $C_{18}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 65.46 ; H, 5.46%).

3,3'-Diallyl-4,4'-dihydroxyphenyl sulfone :

The above ether (0.5 g) was refluxed in diphenyl ether (5 ml) for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was dissolved in ether and extracted with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The product obtained on acidification of the clear alkaline extract crystallised from xylene in white needles (0.3 g), m.p. 151-52°. (Found : C, 65.31 ; H, 5.15, $C_{18}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 65.46 ; H, 5.46%).

Bi(2-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) sulfone :

The above diallyl derivative (1 g) was acetylated by heating with sodium acetate (2 g) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) on a steam bath for 4 hr. The diacetoxy derivative was dissolved in chloroform and treated with bromine (1 g) in chloroform (10 ml). The product obtained on removal of chloroform was refluxed with ethanolic potassium hydroxide (1.5 g) OH in 50 ml alcohol) for 6 hr. The solvent was evaporated and the residue washed with water. The alkali insoluble product crystallised from alcohol in yellowish-brown buds (0.2 g), m.p. 154-55° (Found : C, 66.68 ; H, 4.58, $C_{18}H_{14}O_4S$ requires C, 66.26 ; H, 4.29%). IR, 885 cm^{-1} (Furan ring breathing) UV λ_{max} (chloroform) 244, 290 nm.

4,4'-Diacetoxy diphenyl ether :

Obtained by heating 4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether (3 g), acetic anhydride (15 ml) and sodium acetate (5 g) for 2 hr. and crystallised from alcohol in needles (1.3 g) gave m.p. 112°. (Found : C, 67.03 ; H, 4.83, $C_{16}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 67.03 ; H, 4.89%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether :

An intimate mixture of 4,4'-diacetoxy diphenyl ether (2 g) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g) was heated in an oil bath at 14° for 3 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 185°, yield 0.8 g. It gave a violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 66.70 ; H, 4.66, $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.13 ; H, 4.89%).

Bi(2-methyl-6-chromonyl) ether :

A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether (15 g) ethyl acetate (15 ml) and pulverised sodium (2 g) was refluxed on a steam bath for 8 hr. The pasty mass obtained on acidification was treated repeatedly with petroleum ether and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether-mixture. m.p. 213°, yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 71.97 ; H, 3.86, $C_{26}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 71.86 ; H, 4.19%). It was found insoluble in alkali and did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. IR 1650 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$).

Bi(2-methyl-3-acetyl-6-chromonyl) ether :

A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether (1.5 g) acetic anhydride (15 ml) and fused sodium acetate (6 g) was refluxed in an oil bath for 10 hr. at 180-90°. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in cold water was washed with dilute alkali and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 212°, yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 68.84 ; H, 4.70, $C_{24}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 68.90 ; H, 4.30%). IR 1650 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $>C=O$ gr.) and 1680 cm^{-1} $>C=O$ at 3 position).

4,4'-Di(β -cyanoethoxy) diphenyl ether :

A mixture of 4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether (2 g), acrylonitrile (5 ml.) and cupric oxide (0.2 g.) was refluxed for 25 hr. The reaction mixture was then treated with chloroform and the chloroform layer was washed with sodium hydroxide. The product obtained on removal of chloroform was crystallised from alcohol. m.p. 102°, yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 70.31 ; H, 5.25, N, 9.01, $C_{18}H_{16}O_8N_2$ requires C, 70.03 ; H, 5.19 ; N, 9.08%).

4,4'-Di(β -carboxyethoxy)diphenyl ether :

A mixture of the above cyano derivative (1 g) was refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml) for 4 hr. The product obtained was purified by sodium bicarbonate treatment and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 198°, yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 62.63 ; H, 4.83, $C_{18}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 62.79 ; H, 5.23%).

Bi(6-chromononyl) ether :

The above dicarboxylic acid (0.5 g) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (20 g P_2O_5 ; 10 ml α -phosphoric acid) in an oil-bath for 3 hr. at 120°. The product obtained was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.2 g) m.p. 175°. (Found : C, 69.47, H, 4.77, $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 69.68 H, 4.41%).

Bi(6-chromonyl) ether :

A mixture of bi(6-chromanonyl) ether (0.25 g) in diphenyl ether and palladised charcoal (10% ; 0.2 g) was refluxed for 6 hr. The mixture was filtered hot. The product obtained on cooling was cryrtallised from alcohol, m.p. 218°, yield 0.1 g (Found : C, 70.66, H, 3.48, $C_{18}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 70.60 ; H, 3.26%), IR 1640 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$).

Bi(4'-hydroxy-6-coumarinyl) ether :

A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether (1.5 g), diethyl carbonate (20 ml) and pulverised sodium (2 g) was heated on a steam bath for 10 hr. A little alcohol was added to decompose the unreacted sodium followed by cold water and the mixture was washed with ether and acidified. The

product was purified by extraction with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from alcohol. m.p. 302° (decomp), (Found : C, 63.52 ; H, 2.88, C₁₈H₁₀O₇ requires C, 63.92 ; H, 2.95%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-di(carbomethoxy) diphenyl ether :

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether (1 g) was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (0.7 ml) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g), in dry acetone for 5 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in thin shining plates (0.6 g) m.p. 117°, (Found : C, 62.82 ; H, 5.69, C₂₄H₂₆O₉ requires C, 62.88 ; H, 5.67%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-di(carboxymethoxy) diphenyl ether :

The above ester (1 g) was kept in sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml 10%) for the clear liquid on acidification gave a product which was extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The acid obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 176°, yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 59.36 ; H, 4.86, C₂₀H₁₈O₉ requires C, 59.70 ; H, 4.47%).

Bi(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) ether

The above dicarboxylic acid (0.5 g) was refluxed with sodium acetate (1 g) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) for 1 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was crystallised from alcohol in thick needles (0.2 g), m.p. 78°, (Found : C, 77.80 ; H, 5.32, C₁₈H₁₄O₈ requires C, 77.71 ; H, 5.03%), IR. 885 cm⁻¹ (Furan ring breathing) UV λ_{max} (chloroform) 258,290 nm.

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dibenzoyloxy diphenyl ether :

A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether (1.5 g) in pyridine, and benzoyl chloride (2 ml) was kept at room temperature for 1.5 hr. The reaction mixture was treated with cold hydrochloric acid (1 : 1). The pasty mass was purified by washing with sodium bicarbonate solution and hot water. It crystallised from acetic acid m.p. 127°, yield 0.5 g (Found, C, 73.36, H, 4.66, C₃₀H₂₂O₇ requires C, 72.88, H, 4.45%).

3,3'-Di(benzoyl acetyl)-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl ether :

A solution of the above benzoyloxy derivative (1.5 g) in pyridine was mixed with powdered potassium hydroxide (9 g) and kept for 4 hr. at room temperature. The product obtained on adding

hydrochloric acid was extracted with sodium hydroxide solution. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from benzene, m.p. 163°, yield 0.8 g (Found : C, 72.49 ; H, 4.35, C₃₀H₂₂O₇ requires C, 72.88 ; H, 4.45%).

Bi(6-flavonyl) ether :

The above β-diketone derivative (0.5 g) was mixed with conc. sulphuric acid and the reaction mixture was kept overnight. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water crystallised from acetic acid. m.p. 257°, yield 0.2 g (Found : C, 73.13, H, 4.29, C₃₀H₁₈O₈·2H₂O requires C, 72.88 ; H, 4.45%), IR. 1645 cm⁻¹ (>C=O group).

I

X	R ₁	R ₂
a	SO ₂	C ₆ H ₅
b	O	CH ₃
c	O	COCH ₃
d	O	H
e	O	C ₆ H ₅

II

X	R ₁	R ₂
a	SO ₂	H
b	SO ₂	CH ₃
c	O	H

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